

Derivations Leading to Ampere's Force Law

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Abstract

This paper paraphrases from this author's perspective some of the derivations of Andre-Marie Ampere relating to formulation of what became known as "Ampere's Force Law". It is compared to Neumann's Force Law and it is shown that both are equivalent in force predictions between parallel wires, but not for collinear (in-line) wire segments. Ampere's Force Law predicts a repelling force for collinear wire segments; Neumann's Force Law predicts an attractive force, not in agreement with the interpretation of observations by Ampere and other investigators.

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A Pair of Current Carrying Wires.

1 Current Elements in Three Dimensions

Consider two position vectors in three dimensions. In the figure below, \mathbf{R}_1 is the position vector of incremental wire segment $d\mathbf{s}_1$ located at point P_1 ; \mathbf{R}_2 is the position vector of incremental wire segment $d\mathbf{s}_2$ located at point P_2 and \mathbf{R} (aka \mathbf{R}_{21}) = $\mathbf{R}_2 - \mathbf{R}_1$.

Figure 1: Incremental Path Length Vectors in the Laboratory Coordinate System.

It is difficult to visualize objects that extend in three dimensions via figures on the written page (two dimensions). Note that the angles ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , ϵ do not generally lie in the plane $O-P_1-P_2$ occupied by the vectors \mathbf{R}_1 , \mathbf{R}_2 and \mathbf{R} .

Definitions:

Collinear: in the same straight line; any number of points are said to be collinear or in-line if there is a straight line passing through all of them.

Parallel: extending in the same direction in the same plane and at the same transverse (perpendicular) distance apart at every point.

Longitudinal force: a force in-line with, i.e, collinear to the current flows.

Transverse force: a force at right angles to the current flows.

We will be considering transverse forces between parallel elements and longitudinal forces between collinear elements.

In Figure 1, the vector $d\mathbf{s}_1$ is displayed pointing to the left with an obtuse angle $\epsilon_1 > \frac{\pi}{2}$, because otherwise the figure would be too cluttered were $d\mathbf{s}_1$ displayed at an acute angle to \mathbf{R} . In creating geometric figures in two dimensions, I usually strive as a default measure (for clarity) to portray vectors in the first quadrant using *acute* angles (my default format). Likewise, in three dimensions, I strive to display vectors in the first octant using *acute* angles. Hence, if I were to create Figure 1 in this (cluttered) default format, the vector components $ds_{1\parallel}$ and $ds_{2\parallel}$ would *both* be pointing to the right along the vector \mathbf{R} . However, in the present Figure 1, $ds_{1\parallel}$ is pointing to the left. $ds_{1\parallel}$ and $ds_{2\parallel}$ are components of $d\mathbf{s}_1$ and $d\mathbf{s}_2$ respectively in-line with (collinear to) the vector \mathbf{R} . $v_{1\perp}$ and $v_{2\perp}$ are components of $d\mathbf{s}_1$ and $d\mathbf{s}_2$ respectively perpendicular to the vector \mathbf{R} .

1.0.1 Vector Relations

Consider the following dot products:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_1 \cdot \mathbf{R}_2 &= R_1 R_2 \cos \gamma = x_1 x_2 + y_1 y_2 + z_1 z_2 \\ &= R_1 \sin \phi_1 \cos \theta_1 R_2 \sin \phi_2 \cos \theta_2 + R_1 \sin \phi_1 \sin \theta_1 R_2 \sin \phi_2 \sin \theta_2 + R_1 \cos \phi_1 R_2 \cos \phi_2 \\ \cos \gamma &= \cos \phi_1 \cos \phi_2 + \sin \phi_1 \sin \phi_2 \underbrace{(\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta_2 + \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta_2)}_{\cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1)} \\ \therefore \boxed{\cos \gamma = \cos \phi_1 \cos \phi_2 + \sin \phi_1 \sin \phi_2 \cos \Delta\theta, \quad \Delta\theta = \theta_2 - \theta_1} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Also, } \boxed{R^2 = R_1^2 + R_2^2 - 2R_1 R_2 \cos \gamma}$$

Likewise, in the x-y plane,

$$\boxed{r^2 = r_1^2 + r_2^2 - 2r_1 r_2 \cos \Delta\theta ; \quad \Delta\theta = \theta_2 - \theta_1}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_1 \cdot \mathbf{R} &= R_1 R \cos \gamma_1 = x_1 x + y_1 y + z_1 z \\ &= (R_1 \sin \phi_1 \cos \theta_1) (R \sin \phi \cos \theta) + (R_1 \sin \phi_1 \sin \theta_1) (R \sin \phi \sin \theta) + (R_1 \cos \phi_1) (R \cos \phi) \\ \cos \gamma_1 &= \cos \phi_1 \cos \phi + \sin \phi_1 \sin \phi \underbrace{(\cos \theta_1 \cos \theta + \sin \theta_1 \sin \theta)}_{\cos(\theta - \theta_1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \boxed{\cos \gamma_1 = \cos \phi_1 \cos \phi + \sin \phi_1 \sin \phi \cos \Delta\theta_1, \quad \Delta\theta_1 = \theta - \theta_1} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_2 \cdot \mathbf{R} &= R_2 R \cos \gamma_2 = x_2 x + y_2 y + z_2 z \\ &= R_2 \sin \phi_2 \cos \theta_2 R \sin \phi \cos \theta + R_2 \sin \phi_2 \sin \theta_2 R \sin \phi \sin \theta + R_2 \cos \phi_2 R \cos \phi \\ \cos \gamma_2 &= \cos \phi_2 \cos \phi + \sin \phi_2 \sin \phi \underbrace{(\cos \theta_2 \cos \theta + \sin \theta_2 \sin \theta)}_{\cos(\theta - \theta_2)} \\ \therefore \boxed{\cos \gamma_2 = \cos \phi_2 \cos \phi + \sin \phi_2 \sin \phi \cos \Delta\theta_2, \quad \Delta\theta_2 = \theta - \theta_2} \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{R}_1 = \mathbf{i}x_1 + \mathbf{j}y_1 + \mathbf{j}z_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{R}_2 = \mathbf{i}x_2 + \mathbf{j}y_2 + \mathbf{j}z_2$$

Instead of writing $\Delta x = x_2 - x_1$, $\Delta y = y_2 - y_1$, $\Delta z = z_2 - z_1$, we shall dispense with the deltas and simply write $x = x_2 - x_1$, $y = y_2 - y_1$, $z = z_2 - z_1$.

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_2 - \mathbf{R}_1$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R} &= \mathbf{i}(x_2 - x_1) + \mathbf{j}(y_2 - y_1) + \mathbf{j}(z_2 - z_1) = \mathbf{i}x + \mathbf{j}y + \mathbf{j}z \\ &= \mathbf{i}R \sin \phi \cos \theta + \mathbf{j}R \sin \phi \sin \theta + \mathbf{k}R \cos \phi \end{aligned}$$

$$R = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$$

$$R^2 = (x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2$$

$$2R \frac{dR}{dx_2} = 2(x_2 - x_1)(+1) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{dR}{dx_2} = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{R}$$

$$\text{Likewise, } \frac{dR}{dy_2} = \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dR}{dz_2} = \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R}$$

$$2R \frac{dR}{dx_1} = 2(x_2 - x_1)(-1) \quad \Rightarrow \quad \frac{dR}{dx_1} = -\frac{x_2 - x_1}{R}$$

$$\text{and } \frac{dR}{dy_1} = -\frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dR}{dz_1} = -\frac{z_2 - z_1}{R}$$

$$\Rightarrow \quad dx_2 = -dx_1, \quad dy_2 = -dy_1 \quad \text{and} \quad dz_2 = -dz_1$$

Since \mathbf{R}_1 , \mathbf{R}_2 , and the line segment R all lie in the same \mathcal{O} - P_1 - P_2 plane,

$$\gamma + (\pi - \gamma_1) + \gamma_2 = \pi \quad \Rightarrow \quad \gamma = \gamma_1 - \gamma_2$$

Refer to Figure 1 for meaning of angles γ , γ_1 and γ_2 .

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathbf{s}_2 &= d\mathbf{R}_2 = \mathbf{i}dx_2 + \mathbf{j}dy_2 + \mathbf{k}dz_2 & \text{and} & & ds_2^2 &= dx_2^2 + dy_2^2 + dz_2^2 \\ d\mathbf{s}_1 &= d\mathbf{R}_1 = \mathbf{i}dx_1 + \mathbf{j}dy_1 + \mathbf{k}dz_1 & & & ds_1^2 &= dx_1^2 + dy_1^2 + dz_1^2 \end{aligned}$$

where it is understood that ds_k^2 in this context is shorthand for $(ds_k)^2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R} \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2 &= R ds_2 \cos \epsilon_2 = (x_2 - x_1)dx_2 + (y_2 - y_1)dy_2 + (z_2 - z_1)dz_2 \\ \Rightarrow & \boxed{\cos \epsilon_2 = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \frac{dx_2}{ds_2} + \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \frac{dy_2}{ds_2} + \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \frac{dz_2}{ds_2}} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R} \cdot d\mathbf{s}_1 &= R ds_1 \cos \epsilon_1 = (x_2 - x_1)dx_1 + (y_2 - y_1)dy_1 + (z_2 - z_1)dz_1 \\ \Rightarrow & \boxed{\cos \epsilon_1 = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} + \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \frac{dz_1}{ds_1}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$d\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2 = ds_1 ds_2 \cos \epsilon = dx_1 dx_2 + dy_1 dy_2 + dz_1 dz_2$$

$$\cos \epsilon = \frac{dx_1 dx_2 + dy_1 dy_2 + dz_1 dz_2}{ds_1 ds_2} = \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} \frac{dx_2}{ds_2} + \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} \frac{dy_2}{ds_2} + \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \frac{dz_2}{ds_2}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2 &= dx_1 dx_2 + dy_1 dy_2 + dz_1 dz_2 \\ &= ds_1 ds_2 \cos \epsilon, \quad \text{where } \epsilon = \angle(d\mathbf{s}_1, d\mathbf{s}_2) \end{aligned}$$

Derivatives: In the derivations that follow we shall, like Ampere, dispense with expressing partial derivatives and differential expressions using two symbols " ∂ " and " d "; rather, we shall simply employ the one symbol " d ". Indeed, in the opinion of this author, since the independent variables involved (e.g., R and \mathbf{F}_{21}) have functional dependency on two levels of independent variables (e.g., on s_1, s_2 and x, y, z), there is no benefit in using the extra symbol " ∂ ".

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dR}{ds_2} &= \frac{dR}{dx_2} \frac{dx_2}{ds_2} + \frac{dR}{dy_2} \frac{dy_2}{ds_2} + \frac{dR}{dz_2} \frac{dz_2}{ds_2} \\ &= \left(\frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \right) \frac{dx_2}{ds_2} + \left(\frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \right) \frac{dy_2}{ds_2} + \left(\frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \right) \frac{dz_2}{ds_2} = \cos \epsilon_2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dR}{ds_1} &= \frac{dR}{dx_1} \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \frac{dR}{dy_1} \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} + \frac{dR}{dz_1} \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \\ &= \left(-\frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \right) \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \left(-\frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \right) \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} + \left(-\frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \right) \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} = -\cos \epsilon_1 \end{aligned} \quad (7a)$$

We repeat and highlight these two scalar derivatives here.

$$\boxed{\frac{dR}{ds_2} = \cos \epsilon_2 \quad \text{and similarly,} \quad \frac{dR}{ds_1} = -\cos \epsilon_1}$$

A series of invocations of the chain rule for differentiation follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} &= \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) = \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(-\frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} - \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} - \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \right) \\ &= - \left[\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \right) \right] \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} - \left[\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \right) \right] \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} - \left[\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \right) \right] \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \end{aligned}$$

and, of course, $\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{dx_1}{ds_1} \right) = 0$, $\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{dy_1}{ds_1} \right) = 0$, $\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \right) = 0$, because the positions of ds_1 and ds_2 are independent of one another.

Keeping in mind that there are three terms,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} &= - \left[\frac{1}{R} \frac{d(x_2 - x_1)}{ds_2} + (x_2 - x_1) \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(\frac{1}{R} \right) \right] \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \dots + etc. \\ &= - \left[\frac{1}{R} \frac{d(x_2 - x_1)}{dx_2} \frac{dx_2}{ds_2} + (x_2 - x_1) (-R^{-2}) \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right] \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \dots + etc. \\ &= - \left(\frac{1}{R} \frac{dx_2}{ds_2} - \frac{x_2 - x_1}{R^2} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} - \left(\frac{1}{R} \frac{dy_2}{ds_2} - \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R^2} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} - \left(\frac{1}{R} \frac{dz_2}{ds_2} - \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R^2} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \\ &= - \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{dx_2}{ds_2} - \frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} - \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{dy_2}{ds_2} - \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} - \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{dz_2}{ds_2} - \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging terms,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} &= - \frac{1}{R} \underbrace{\left(\frac{dx_2}{ds_2} \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \frac{dy_2}{ds_2} \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} + \frac{dz_2}{ds_2} \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \right)}_{\cos \epsilon} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{R} \underbrace{\frac{dR}{ds_2}}_{\cos \epsilon_2} \underbrace{\left(\frac{x_2 - x_1}{R} \frac{dx_1}{ds_1} + \frac{y_2 - y_1}{R} \frac{dy_1}{ds_1} + \frac{z_2 - z_1}{R} \frac{dz_1}{ds_1} \right)}_{\cos \epsilon_1} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where

$$\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{n}_{21} = \frac{\mathbf{R}}{|\mathbf{R}|} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_{21} = \mathbf{R}_2 - \mathbf{R}_1$$

Thus, according to this model as it is so far considered, for two straight *parallel* wire increments, $d^2 F_{21} = -k' \frac{i_1 i_2 ds_1 ds_2}{R^2}$; for two straight mutually *perpendicular* wire increments, $d^2 F_{21} = 0$. Neumann's force law obeys Newton's 3rd law.

In the derivations above we have measured *both* of the angles ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 in the conventional manner, counter-clockwise (CCW) from the axis of the vector \mathbf{R} to ds_1 and ds_2 respectively (Ref. Figs. 1 and 4). However, as mentioned earlier, in Ampere's original derivation, instead of using the angle ϵ_2 , Ampere considered the *interior* angle $\pi - \epsilon_2$ which we designate as $\epsilon_3 = \pi - \epsilon_2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \cos \epsilon_2 = \frac{dR}{ds_2} \quad \Rightarrow \quad \cos \epsilon_3 = -\frac{dR}{ds_2} \quad \text{and} \\ \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_3 = \left(-\frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) \left(-\frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) = \frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} &= -\frac{1}{R} (\cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_3 + \cos \epsilon) \\ &= -\frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} + \cos \epsilon \right), \quad \text{Ampere's version.} \end{aligned}$$

Note: $d^2 F_{21}$ in the equation above is positive for a repulsive force. Ampere, however, associated a positive $d^2 F_{21}$ with an attractive force, and so, his equation did not have the minus sign. We shall retain the minus sign.

1.0.2 Incremental Path Lengths in the Laboratory Coordinate System S

Below are displayed the spherical coordinates of vectors ds_1 , ds_2 in the laboratory coordinate System S . We have relocated these vectors to the origin \mathcal{O} .

$\cos \epsilon$ does not specifically depend upon the angles δ_1 and δ_2 , rather just upon their difference $\Delta\delta$. This equation and similar equations relating to the laboratory coordinate System S are not required in our present discussion. Rather, we will focus on the coordinate System S' .

From Figure 1,

$$\epsilon_1 = \angle(\mathbf{R}, ds_1) \quad , \quad \epsilon_2 = \angle(\mathbf{R}, ds_2) \quad , \quad \epsilon = \angle(ds_1, ds_2) \quad , \quad \mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{R}}{R}$$

$$ds_1 \cdot \mathbf{R} = R ds_1 \cos \epsilon_1 \quad , \quad ds_2 \cdot \mathbf{R} = R ds_2 \cos \epsilon_2$$

that is,

$$ds_1 \cdot \mathbf{n} = ds_1 \cos \epsilon_1 \quad , \quad ds_2 \cdot \mathbf{n} = ds_2 \cos \epsilon_2$$

1.0.3 Incremental Path Lengths in the Auxiliary Coordinate System S'

Aligning the vector \mathbf{R} vertically.

Suppose that we consider the vectors \mathbf{R} , ds_1 and ds_2 from Figure 1 in another (rotated) coordinate system $S'(x', y', z')$ with the vector \mathbf{R} pointing up along the positive z' axis and the co-azimuthal plane on the bottom of the page. By doing this we more easily visualize these vectors and \mathbf{R} in spherical coordinates as in Figure 3 below. For the time being we do not specify the orientation of the rotation plane and axes η_1 and η_2 relative to the laboratory coordinate system S .

Figure 3: Incremental Path Lengths in System S' .

In Figure 4 below we present another portrayal of the various line segments and angles relevant to our discussion.

Figure 4: Another Representation of the Wire Segments in Systems S and S' .

Since we are dealing with vectors, ds_1 and ds_2 can be mathematically manipulated as if they radiate out from the origin \mathcal{O} .

We had previously expanded the dot product $ds_1 \cdot ds_2$ in terms of the angles $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \delta_1, \delta_2$ in the Laboratory System S . Similarly we now do an expansion of $ds_1 \cdot ds_2$ in terms of the angles $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, \eta_1, \eta_2$ in the Embedded System S' .

$$ds_1 = \mathbf{i} ds_1 \sin \epsilon_1 \cos \eta_1 + \mathbf{j} ds_1 \sin \epsilon_1 \sin \eta_1 + \mathbf{k} ds_1 \cos \epsilon_1$$

$$ds_2 = \mathbf{i} ds_2 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \eta_2 + \mathbf{j} ds_2 \sin \epsilon_2 \sin \eta_2 + \mathbf{k} ds_2 \cos \epsilon_2$$

$$\begin{aligned} ds_1 \cdot ds_2 &= ds_1 ds_2 \cos \epsilon \\ &= ds_1 \sin \epsilon_1 \cos \eta_1 ds_2 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \eta_2 + ds_1 \sin \epsilon_1 \sin \eta_1 ds_2 \sin \epsilon_2 \sin \eta_2 + ds_1 \cos \epsilon_1 ds_2 \cos \epsilon_2 \\ \cos \epsilon &= \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2 + \sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \underbrace{(\cos \eta_1 \cos \eta_2 + \sin \eta_1 \sin \eta_2)}_{\cos(\eta_2 - \eta_1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \boxed{\cos \epsilon = \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2 + \sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \Delta \eta, \quad \Delta \eta = \eta_2 - \eta_1} \quad (12)$$

1.0.4 Interpretations of Ampere's writings.

Ampere postulated two components of magnetic force directed along vector \mathbf{R} . His assumptions were to be accepted or rejected based upon outcomes of experiments conducted by himself, Michael Faraday and others.

When we considered *Neumann's force law*, $d^2F_{21} = -k' \frac{i_1 i_2 (d\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2)}{R^2}$, which involves only one term on the right hand side of the equation, we employed the constant k' . The validity of this equation is supported by its agreement with the integrated form of Ampere's Law, $\frac{F_{21}}{l} = -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r}$, which is verified by experiments on parallel long wires, one infinite in length and the other of length l . (r is the distance of wire separation).

However, in experiments of Faraday and Ampere, especially in Ampere's famous "hairpin" experiment, wire movements were observed that were consistent with a *repulsive* force between collinear (in-line) current elements, rather than a force of attraction which would be predicted by Neumann's force law. Consequently, Ampere needed to start anew in formulating an equation describing this force d^2F_{21} , using *two* terms on the right hand side of the equation. The first term is the same as the term in Neumann's force law. *A priori*, we may not presume that the proportionality constant will remain the same. Consequently, for this purpose we shall employ another constant, k_A .

Current Components Perpendicular to \mathbf{R} .

Ampere first considered the components of $d\mathbf{s}_1$ and $d\mathbf{s}_2$ that were *perpendicular* to \mathbf{R} . He *guessed* that the magnetic force along \mathbf{R} exerted on the component of $d\mathbf{s}_2$ perpendicular to \mathbf{R} by the component of $d\mathbf{s}_1$ perpendicular to \mathbf{R} is given by the following proportion:

$$d^2F_{21\perp} \propto \frac{\sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \Delta\eta}{R^2}, \text{ where } \Delta\eta = \eta_2 - \eta_1$$

This portion of d^2F_{21} is derived from current flows perpendicular to \mathbf{R} , so we designate it as $d^2F_{21\perp}$ (or d^2F_{21r}); that is,

$$d^2F_{21\perp} = -k_A i_1 d\mathbf{s}_1 i_2 d\mathbf{s}_2 \frac{\sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \Delta\eta}{R^2}$$

(Motive for r subscript: the component is a radial component in the x' - y' plane of rotated System S'). Figure 4 may be useful in visualizing this force.

This is just what we might expect, given basic observations that two stationary parallel wires in the laboratory attract one another if the currents flow in the same direction.

Current Components In-Line with \mathbf{R} .

Ampere also considered a (possible) additional component of magnetic force d^2F_{21} along \mathbf{R} due to components of current flow through differential segments ds_1 and ds_2 that are in-line with \mathbf{R} .

A priori, there was no reason to assume that this force was zero.

Note: In most contemporary physics textbooks, this force is implicitly considered to be zero.

Label this force $d^2F_{21\parallel}$ (or d^2F_{21z}). Consider again the rotated coordinate System S' .

$$d^2F_{21\parallel} \propto \frac{m \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2}{R^2}$$

where m is a constant to be determined by experiment.

$$d^2F_{21\parallel} = -k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2 \frac{m \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2}{R^2}$$

Thus, in the spirit of Ampere's investigations, we might paraphrase as follows: The incremental magnetic force exerted on $i_2 ds_2$ of circuit 2 by $i_1 ds_1$ of circuit 1 is directed along vector \mathbf{R} and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} d^2F_{21} &= d^2F_{21\perp} + d^2F_{21\parallel} \\ &= -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} (\sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \Delta\eta + m \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

As we have shown for System S' ,

$$\cos \epsilon = \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2 + \sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \Delta\eta, \quad \Delta\eta = \eta_2 - \eta_1 \quad (14)$$

$$\therefore \sin \epsilon_1 \sin \epsilon_2 \cos \Delta\eta = \cos \epsilon - \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2 \quad (15)$$

$\cos \epsilon$ does not specifically depend upon the angles η_1 and η_2 , rather just upon their difference $\Delta\eta$.

Then,

$$d^2F_{21} = -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} [(\cos \epsilon - \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2) + m \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2]$$

$$d^2F_{21} = -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} [\cos \epsilon + (m - 1) \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2]$$

That is,

$$\frac{d^2F_{21}}{ds_1 ds_2} = -\frac{k_A i_1 i_2}{R^2} [\cos \epsilon + (m - 1) \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2]$$

Except for the final term on the right hand side, this equation is of the same form and content as Neumann's Force Law.

As derived previously,

$$\begin{aligned}\cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2 &= -\frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \\ \cos \epsilon &= -\frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} - R \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} \\ \cos \epsilon &= \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(R \frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) = -\frac{d}{ds_2} (R \cos \epsilon_1) \\ &= \frac{d}{ds_1} \left(R \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) = \frac{d}{ds_1} (R \cos \epsilon_2)\end{aligned}$$

so,

$$\begin{aligned}d^2 F_{21} &= -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} \left[\left(-\frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} - R \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} \right) + (m-1) \left(-\frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right) \right] \\ d^2 F_{21} &= -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} \left(-R \frac{d^2 R}{ds_1 ds_2} - m \frac{dR}{ds_1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \right)\end{aligned}\tag{16}$$

1.0.5 Digression: Determining the value of the parameter m .

Graneau recounts [4, page 12] that Ampere performed a null experiment and observed that the *mechanical* force exerted *tangentially* on "a circular arc section of a current carrying circuit 2" by another circuit 1 which is in an arbitrary relative orientation to it is zero¹. He detected no movement of wire arc 2 that might be from a component of magnetic force in-line with that wire (that is, tangential to the wire arc 2). We highlight "mechanical" force above to indicate that only movements of the mechanical arm were observable, not of "electrons" or other microscopic unobservable agents which might be judged as accountable for the magnetic force. The circular arc is capable of rotation around an axis perpendicular to the plane of the arc, i.e., along its tangent. This observation that wire arc 2 did not move enabled him to compute the value of the parameter m . We will pursue his line of reasoning below.

Consider Ampere's experiment and an English translation of his main work by Torres and Chaib [1]. There is no component of the force along the direction of the current element. Thus, we might state that two *parallel* wires carrying currents i_1 and i_2 will experience no mechanical force between them *in the direction of the wires*. However, Ampere's force law does consider the possibility of an *in-line* mechanical force between sections of the same straight wire exerted along that wire.

Consider the derivative

$$\frac{d}{ds_2} \left(R^m \frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) = m R^{m-1} \frac{dR}{ds_2} \frac{dR}{ds_1} + R^m \frac{d^2 R}{ds_2 ds_1}$$

¹Graneau's circuit 1 is our circuit 2 and vice versa.

Dividing both sides by R^{m-1} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{R^{m-1}} \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(R^m \frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) &= m \frac{dR}{ds_2} \frac{dR}{ds_1} + R \frac{d^2 R}{ds_2 ds_1} \Rightarrow \\ d^2 F_{21} &= -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} \left[-\frac{1}{R^{m-1}} \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(R^m \frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) \right] \\ d^2 F_{21} &= k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2 R^{-(m+1)} \frac{d}{ds_2} \left(R^m \frac{dR}{ds_1} \right) \end{aligned}$$

But $\frac{dR}{ds_1} = -\cos \epsilon_1 \Rightarrow$

$$d^2 F_{21} = -k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2 R^{-(m+1)} \frac{d}{ds_2} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1)$$

Multiply both sides of this equation by $\cos \epsilon_1$ to get the component of the incremental magnetic force in line with $d\mathbf{s}_1$.

$$d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1 = -k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2 \cos \epsilon_1 R^{-(m+1)} \frac{d}{ds_2} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1)$$

Rewrite this equation, noting that $R^{-(m+1)} = R^{-(2m+1)} R^m$.

$$d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1 = -k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2 R^{-(2m+1)} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1) \frac{d}{ds_2} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1)$$

Consider again Figure 4.

Integrate along the closed path of wire 2. The position vector \mathbf{R}_1 of $d\mathbf{s}_1$ is held constant during this integration. However, the vector \mathbf{R} varies, and consequently, so does the angle $\epsilon_1 = \angle(\mathbf{R}, d\mathbf{s}_1)$. So we may not remove it to outside of the integral sign.

$$\oint_2 d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1 = -k_A i_1 i_2 ds_1 \left[\oint_2 R^{-(2m+1)} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1) \frac{d}{ds_2} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1) ds_2 \right]$$

We will integrate by parts this equation, noting that $d(uv) = u dv + v du \Rightarrow \int u dv = uv - \int v du$,

$$\int u dv = \int d(uv) - \int v du, \quad \oint u dv = \oint d(uv) - \oint v du, \text{ where}$$

$$u = R^{-(2m+1)}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial s_2} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial R} \frac{\partial R}{\partial s_2} = -(2m+1) R^{-2(m+1)} \frac{\partial R}{\partial s_2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \partial u = -(2m + 1) R^{-2(m+1)} \partial R$$

$$dv = (R^m \cos \epsilon_1) \frac{d}{ds_2} (R^m \cos \epsilon_1) ds_2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad v = \frac{1}{2} R^{2m} \cos^2 \epsilon_1$$

and, for any limits on integration, c and d , $uv = \int_c^d d \left(\frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{2R} \right) = \frac{1}{2R} \cos^2 \epsilon_1 \Big|_c^d$

Circuit 2 is along a closed path (a Jordan curve), so we use the line integral \oint_2 ;

the upper and lower limits are the same. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \oint_2 d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1 &= \\ & -k_A i_1 i_2 ds_1 \left\{ \oint_2 d \left(\frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{2R} \right) - \oint_2 \left(\frac{1}{2} R^{2m} \cos^2 \epsilon_1 \right) [-(2m + 1) R^{-2(m+1)} dR] \right\} \\ \oint_2 d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1 &= -k_A i_1 i_2 ds_1 \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{R} \Big|_{s_2(i)}^{s_2(f)} + (2m + 1) \oint_2 \frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{R^2} dR \right) = 0 \\ \oint_2 d \left(\frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{R} \right) &= \frac{1}{R} \cos^2 \epsilon_1 \Big|_{s_2(i)}^{s_2(f)} = 0, \text{ where } i = \text{"initial"} \text{ and } f = \text{"final"} \end{aligned}$$

Based upon Ampere's experiments, the integral $\oint_2 d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1$ should be equal to zero.

$$\oint_2 d^2 F_{21} \cos \epsilon_1 = -k_A i_1 i_2 ds_1 \frac{2m + 1}{2} \oint_2 \frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{R^2} dR = 0$$

Graneau [4, page 13] states that "As Ampere pointed out, however, many closed circuits can be imagined for which the integral in the second term... will not vanish".

That is, the integral $\oint_2 \frac{\cos^2 \epsilon_1}{R^2} dR$ is not generally equal to zero.

$$\therefore 2m + 1 = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad m = -\frac{1}{2}$$

This value is independent of the constant k_A and of the units with which we measure the currents and lengths.

End of digression.

Therefore, based upon Faraday's experiments, Ampere decided that $m = -\frac{1}{2}$, so

$$d^2 F_{21\parallel} = k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2 \frac{\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2}{R^2}, \text{ and so}$$

$$d^2 F_{21} = -\frac{k_A i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} \left(\cos \epsilon - \frac{3}{2} \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2 \right)$$

Thus, Ampere includes an additional measure of in-line or collinear force proportional to $-\frac{3}{2} \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2$. This is due to results that he and others obtained in his bridge ("hairpin") experiments.

To ascertain the value of k_A , we doubly integrate this equation appropriately to obtain the magnetic force between two parallel wires, one of infinite length and the other of finite length l . We obtain

$$\frac{F_{21}}{l} = \frac{F_{21}}{l} = -k_A \frac{i_1 i_2}{r}; \text{ But this must be equivalent to } \frac{F_{21}}{l} = -2k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{r}$$

So it turns out that the constant $k_A = 2k'$. The reader is referred to [5] for validation of this claim. Suppose that this substitution is made in the previous equation. Then,

$$\boxed{d^2 F_{21} = -\frac{k' i_1 ds_1 i_2 ds_2}{R^2} (2 \cos \epsilon - 3 \cos \epsilon_1 \cos \epsilon_2)} \quad (17)$$

$$= -k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{R^2} \left(2 \underbrace{ds_1 ds_2}_{ds_1 \cdot ds_2} \cos \epsilon - 3 \underbrace{ds_1 \cos \epsilon_1}_{\mathbf{n} \cdot ds_1} \underbrace{ds_2 \cos \epsilon_2}_{\mathbf{n} \cdot ds_2} \right)$$

After subjecting this equation to two integrations, for two parallel long wires, one infinite in length and the other of length l , the result is the same as the result of integrating Neumann's force law, that is, the integrated form of Ampere's force law.

$$\boxed{d^2 \mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' \frac{i_1 i_2}{R^2} \mathbf{n} [2 (ds_1 \cdot ds_2) - 3 (\mathbf{n} \cdot ds_1) (\mathbf{n} \cdot ds_2)] = -d^2 \mathbf{F}_{12}} \quad (18)$$

for infinitesimal current elements ds_1 and ds_2 . Likewise, for the complete current loops:

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \oint_1 \oint_2 \mathbf{n} \left[\frac{2 (ds_1 \cdot ds_2) - 3 (\mathbf{n} \cdot ds_1) (\mathbf{n} \cdot ds_2)}{R^2} \right] = -\mathbf{F}_{12}$$

The equations are symmetrical: They predict that if the two circuit loops are interchanged with $\mathbf{n}_{21} \leftarrow \mathbf{n}_{12}$, the forces are reversed. Thus, Ampere's force law obeys Newton's 3rd law .

$\mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{R}}{R}$ is the unit (position) vector directed along the vector \mathbf{R} from ds_1 to ds_2 .

When we perform the required integrations in Neumann's Force Law, we find that

$$\mathbf{F}_{21} = -k' i_1 i_2 \int_{a=-\infty}^{b=+\infty} \int_c^d \mathbf{n} \frac{d\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2}{R^2} = -\mathbf{e}_r k' \left(\frac{2}{r}\right) l = -\mathbf{e}_r 2k' \frac{i_1 i_2 l}{r}$$

where $l = d - c$ and \mathbf{e}_r is the unit vector in the x-y plane perpendicular to the wires. Similarly, when we perform the required integrations in Ampere's Force Law, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}_{21} &= -k' i_1 i_2 \int_{a=-\infty}^{b=+\infty} \int_c^d \mathbf{n} \left[\frac{2(d\mathbf{s}_1 \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2) - 3(\mathbf{n} \cdot d\mathbf{s}_1)(\mathbf{n} \cdot d\mathbf{s}_2)}{R^2} \right] = \\ &= -\mathbf{e}_r k' i_1 i_2 \left[2 \left(\frac{2}{r}\right) - 3 \left(\frac{2}{3r}\right) \right] l = -\mathbf{e}_r k' i_1 i_2 \left(\frac{4}{r} - \frac{2}{r}\right) l = \\ &= -\mathbf{e}_r k' i_1 i_2 \left(\frac{2}{r}\right) l = -\mathbf{e}_r 2k' \frac{i_1 i_2 l}{r} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, Neumann's Force Law and Ampere's Force Law agree in their predictions of magnetic force between parallel wires.

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